

THERMOELASTIC AND 3D FAILURE ANALYSES OF CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITE BRAKE DISKS

Chun-Gon Kim¹, Jung-Seok Kim¹, Jae-Seok Yu¹, Chang-Sun Hong¹, Byung-Il Yoon²

¹*Department of Aerospace Engineering, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology
Taejon 305-701, Korea*

²*Agency for Defense Development, Taejon 300-600, Korea*

SUMMARY: For the proper design of a carbon-carbon brake disk system, the transient thermoelastic and 3D failure analyses were done using finite element methods. The angular velocity history of the rotor disk was obtained by energy balance method and compared with experimental results. In this study, the 7-disk brake system was studied and tested. In the transient thermoelastic analysis, it was assumed that there is no energy dissipation such as wear. The results of transient thermoelastic analysis such as pressure, friction force and temperature were imposed to the 3D failure analysis for the most severe operating conditions. Then, 3D failure analysis was performed using cyclic symmetry condition. The results of thermoelastic analysis were compared with those of dynamometer test especially for the angular velocity history. The history of angular velocity shows good agreement between the numerical and the experimental results. For the considered brake system, the maximum pressure and the temperature occur at the first friction surface. The disk used in the 3D finite element analysis is the first rotor disk with the first and second friction surfaces. From 3D failure analysis, Tsai-Wu failure index was surveyed for the model. The analyses showed good agreement with the test result and possibly can be used for the slot design of carbon-carbon brake disks.

KEYWORDS: carbon-carbon, brake disk, thermoelastic analysis, 3D failure analysis

INTRODUCTION

In aircraft brake systems, kinetic energy is transformed to heat energy. Aircraft brake systems are usually composed of multiple disks, in which the wheel-driven rotors are sandwiched between stators held stationary by brake structure. Braking action is achieved by pressing the disks using hydraulic pressure, and heat is generated on the contact surfaces of disks. Therefore, materials of brake disks should possess high thermal conductivity and high specific strength at high temperatures. Unlike metals and ceramics, carbon-carbon composites retain their strength at very high temperatures. High thermal conductivity and low thermal expansion give carbon-carbon materials an excellent resistance to thermal shock. Also, the use of carbon-carbon composite brake disks offered 60% weight saving compared with steel[1]. The analyses of temperatures and stresses in the friction disks were performed for steel multi-disk systems[2, 3].

In this study, the transient thermoelastic analysis for carbon-carbon composites was performed and the angular velocity was calculated by energy balance method. In the transient

thermoelastic analysis, it was assumed that there is no energy dissipation such as wear. Then, 3D failure analysis using cyclic symmetry condition was performed.

GOVERNING EQUATION

An implicit transient heat equation is [4, 5]

$$\begin{aligned} & ([C_T] + \beta \Delta t [K_H]) \{T\}_{t+\Delta t} \\ & = ([C_T] - (1 - \beta) \Delta t [K_H]) \{T\}_t + \Delta t \{ (1 - \beta) \{R\}_t + \beta \{R\}_{t+\Delta t} \} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The elastic equation is [4, 5]

$$[K]\{U\} = \{F_f\} + \{F_m\} + \{F_T\} \quad (2)$$

ENERGY BALANCE METHOD

The angular velocity of the rotor disk is a function of the kinetic energy of the aircraft. Therefore, the angular velocity of the rotor disk can be calculated from reduction of kinetic energy by heat generation. The heat generation during Δt is

$$\Delta t \{ (1 - \beta) \{R\}_t + \beta \{R\}_{t+\Delta t} \} \quad (3)$$

TRANSIENT THERMOELASTIC ANALYSIS

This problem is a special case of the contact problem because it is non-isothermal and contact points appear simultaneously on many surfaces. In contact problem, the actual contact area is unknown in advance, therefore, iteration technique is needed. In each friction surfaces, a pair of contacted nodes are defined. One of the nodes is designated as the master node and the other as the slave node. The continuity of axial displacements at this interface is required for the each pair of contact nodes, however, discontinuity of the radial displacements can take place due to the slip.

By the continuity condition of the temperature field, nodal temperatures on the friction surfaces have the following constraint condition.

$$T_{at M} = T_{at S} \quad \text{when } P > 0 \quad (4)$$

By the relation $q^* = \mu Pr \omega$, heat is generated on the contact nodes of the friction surfaces.

$$\begin{aligned} q^* &= \mu Pr \omega \quad \text{when } P > 0 \\ q^* &= 0 \quad \text{otherwise} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 1 shows the finite element model with elastic boundary conditions.

Fig. 1: Axisymmetric finite element model for elastic analysis.

The A-B surface along the radius of the right-end disk at $z=0.0$ [m] is pressed by the hydraulic pressure P_h and called the pressure plate. The C-D surface along the radius of the left-end disk at $z=0.03488$ [m] is fixed and called the end plate. In the present model, there are a pressure plate, an end plate, three rotors and two stators. The thicknesses of the pressure plate and the end plate are 0.01016 [m] and 0.00972[m], respectively. And, the thickness of the rest disk is 0.015 [m]. The inner radius r_i and the outer radius r_o of the disks are 0.089[m] and 0.138[m], respectively. Axisymmetric 8 nodes isoparametric elements were used in the finite element analysis of the brake disk. There are 20 elements and 85 nodes per disk. The model contains 7 disks and the whole system has 140 elements and 595 nodes. Fig. 2 shows the finite element model with heat boundary conditions.

Fig. 2: Axisymmetric finite element model for heat analysis.

The heat boundary conditions are as follow; the adiabatic condition is applied to the two surfaces, the B-C and A-D surfaces bounded by the outer radius r_o and the inner radius r_i and the temperature on the A-B and C-D surfaces has prescribed temperature boundary condition, $T=20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ by the assumption of the cooling state like air-blowing. Fig. 3 shows history of hydraulic pressure. The hydraulic pressure in experiment varied to keep the torque of brake disk constant. In this study, the history of hydraulic pressure was approximated from the results of dynamometer test. The implicit transient time step $\Delta t = 0.01$ second was used in the calculations. The initial kinetic energy and the initial angular velocity of the brake system were 7752kJ and 209rad/sec.

Fig. 3: History of hydraulic pressure.

Table 1 shows the material properties of carbon-carbon composites for the axisymmetric transient thermoelastic analysis.

Table 1: Material Properties of Carbon-Carbon Composites For the Transient Thermoelastic Analysis.

Properties	Symbol	value
Elastic modulus in r	E_r	^a 59 GPa
Elastic modulus in z	E_z	^a 3.46 GPa
Shear modulus in r-z	G_{rz}	1.38 GPa
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_{r\theta}$	0.3
Poisson's ratio	ν_{rz}	0.2
Thermal expansion coeff. in r	α_r	0.31×10^{-6} 1/K
Thermal expansion coeff. in z	α_z	0.29×10^{-6} 1/K
Thermal conductivity in r	k_r	50 W/(m K)
Thermal conductivity in z	k_z	10 W/(m K)
Density	ρ	^a 1.72×10^3 Kg/m ³
Specific heat	c	1.42×10^3 J/(Kg K)
Friction coefficient	$\mu_{t=0}$	^a 0.33

^a: material properties measured from material testing.

RESULTS OF TRANSIENT THERMOELASTIC ANALYSIS

Fig. 4 shows the measured and calculated histories of angular velocity. From Fig. 4, the braking time measured from the dynamometer test was 23 seconds and the one obtained from the analysis was 20 seconds. Therefore, the history of angular velocity shows good agreement between the numerical and experimental results and the angular velocity decreased linearly to keep a constant deceleration. Fig. 5 shows the calculated history of kinetic energy, From the Fig. 5 the kinetic energy decreased exponentially. Fig. 6 shows the calculated history of maximum pressure at first rotor disk. The maximum value is 0.93MPa and occurs at $t = 8$ seconds. After $t = 8$, the maximum pressure decreased almost linearly up to braking time.

Fig. 4: History of angular velocity.

Fig. 5: History of kinetic energy.

Fig. 7 shows the history of maximum temperature at first rotor disk. The maximum value is 1330°C and occur at t = 9 seconds. After t = 9, the maximum temperature also decreased up to braking time.

Fig. 6: History of maximum pressure.

Fig. 7: History of maximum temperature.

3D FAILURE ANALYSIS

The first rotor disk of the 7-disk brake system was observed to be in most severe operating condition, so the first rotor disk with the first and the second friction surfaces was selected for 3D failure analysis. The results imported to 3D analysis are pressure, friction force and temperature. In the present 3D analysis, the modeling of full disk is impossible, because it requires huge computer memory and computing time. However, the rotor has five slots equally spaced along the outer circumference, so the rotor disk is cyclically symmetric with respect to Z axis in terms of geometry and loading. Therefore, for the efficiency of computation, the one fifth of full disk is modeled using cyclic symmetry condition. Fig. 8

shows the cyclic symmetry model of brake system used in this study and displacement boundary condition.

Fig.8: Finite element model and boundary condition of 3D failure analysis.

The 3D failure analysis was performed using commercial package, NISA-II. The 3D model has 944 elements and 5745 nodes. The cyclic symmetry condition means that the displacement of face 1 is the same as the displacement of face 2 as Eqn 6

$$\begin{aligned} U_{r1} &= U_{r2} \\ U_{\theta1} &= U_{\theta2} \\ U_{z1} &= U_{z2} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

This condition was imposed by the multi-point constraints (MPC) in NISA-II. The rotors of brake disk have five key slots. The steel keys connected to the wheel of aircraft are inserted to the key slots. When the braking action is started, the forces generated at the key slots by the keys are equivalent to the friction force. At that time, the displacement of θ -direction at the slots is constrained by the key. Therefore, the boundary condition at key slot is imposed such as Fig. 8. The failure criterion used in 3D failure analysis is Tsai-Wu failure criterion. The Tsai-Wu failure criterion is

$$\begin{aligned} f(\sigma_k) &= F_i \sigma_i + F_{ij} \sigma_{ij} = 1 \\ i, j, k &= 1, 2, \dots, 6 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

RESULTS OF 3D FAILURE ANALYSIS

The 3D failure analysis was performed for the most severe operating condition. The maximum pressure distribution of the brake system occurred at 8 seconds after the application of the hydraulic pressure. Therefore, at that time, the 3D failure analysis was performed. Table 2 shows the material properties of carbon-carbon composite used in the 3D analysis. Some properties were measured by the material tests for this study.

Table 2: 3D Material Properties of Carbon-Carbon Composites.

Properties	Symbol	value
Elastic modulus in r, θ	E_r, E_θ	^a 59 GPa
Elastic modulus in z	E_z	^a 3.46 GPa
Shear modulus in r- θ	$G_{r\theta}$	2.41GPa
Shear modulus in r-z	G_{rz}	1.38GPa
Shear modulus in θ -z	$G_{\theta z}$	1.38 GPa
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_{r\theta}$	0.3
Poisson's ratio	$\nu_{rz}, \nu_{\theta z}$	0.2
Thermal expansion coeff. in r, θ	α_r, α_θ	0.31×10^{-6} 1/K
Thermal expansion coeff. in z	α_z	0.29×10^{-6} 1/K
Tensile strength in r, θ -dirn.		^a 103 MPa
Compressive strength in r, θ -dirn.		^a 90.1 MPa
Tensile strength in z-dirn.		^a 3.01 MPa
Compressive strength in z-dirn.		^a 118 MPa
Shear strength in r- θ plane		34 MPa
Shear strength in r-z plane		^a 5.71 MPa
Shear strength in θ -z plane		^a 5.71 MPa

^a: material properties measured from material testing.

Fig. 9 shows the Tsai-Wu failure index contour of brake disk. From Fig. 9, maximum failure index was 0.59 and occurred at the slot notch. In this failure analysis, stress concentration around the pin holes was not severe.

Fig. 9: Tsai-Wu failure index contour of the carbon-carbon brake disk at slot.

CONCLUSIONS

For carbon-carbon composite brake disk system having 7 disks, the transient thermoelastic and 3D failure analyses were performed. The transient thermoelastic behaviors of composite brake disk based on the experimental dynamometer test conditions were investigated and the angular velocity history was calculated by energy balance method. The hydraulic pressure was approximated from the results of dynamometer test. The history of angular velocity showed good agreement between the numerical and experimental results and decreased linearly. The histories of maximum pressure and the maximum temperature increased until $t=8$ and $t=9$ seconds, respectively and then decreased up to the braking time for the first rotor that is the most severely loaded one. In the 3D failure analysis, the results of transient thermoelastic analysis such as pressure, friction force and temperature were imported to the 3D analysis. The 3D failure analysis was performed at the time of maximum pressure and for the first rotor disk. The maximum failure index occurred at the slot notch and stress concentration around the pin holes was not severe.

REFERENCES

1. Kennedy, F.E. and Ling, F.F.," A Thermal, Thermoelastic and Wear Simulation of A High-Energy Sliding Contact Problem," *J. Lubr. Technol.*, Vol. 97, 1974, pp. 497.
2. Zagrodzki, P.," Numerical Analysis of Temperature Fields and Thermal Stresses in The Friction Discs of A Multidisc Wet Clutch," *Wear*, Vol.101, 1985, pp. 255-271.
3. Zagrodzki, P.," Analysis of Thermomechanical Phenomena in Multidisc Clutches and Brakes," *Wear*, Vol.140, 1990, pp. 291-308.
4. Sonn, H.W., Kim, C. G., Hong, C. S., and Yoon, B. I., "Transient Thermoelastic Analysis of Composite Brake Disks," *J. of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, Vol. 14, Dec., 1995, pp. 1337-1361.
5. Sonn, H.W., Kim, C. G., Hong, C. S., and Yoon, B. I., "Axisymmetric Analysis of Transient Thermoelastic Behaviors in Composite Brake Disks," *J. of Thermophysics and Heat Transfer*, Vol. 10, No. 1, 1996, pp. 67-75.
6. EMRC NISA-II, *User's Manual*, 1992.